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The colour of language! Exploiting non-standard language colour terms semantically for interdisciplinary research (EGI ENGAGE/DARIAH-CC case study)

1. Introduction - the project exploreAT!

This paper describes the exploitation of colour terms for interdisciplinary research. The study is part of a larger collaborative project, *exploreAT!*¹[1], carried out at the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities. The project itself explores the richness of the German language, in particular the *Bavarian dialects in Austria*, in the area of the former Austro-Hungarian empire. It is based on the *Dictionary of Bavarian dialects in Austria* (WBÖ) and the *Database of Bavarian dialects in Austria* (DBÖ). The extensive collection of 20th century dialect data for dictionaries, was harvested by means of questionnaires (~ 20.000) with answers noted on hand-written paper slips containing around 200.000 individual headwords in about 3.5 million individual records. Having undergone different stages of digitisation, the dialect data is currently being encoded in TEI/XML [2] working towards linked open data, mapping onto RDF² and making use of Ontolex [3,4]. Being embedded in the EGI ENGAGE³ /DARIAH-CC⁴ infrastructures, interdisciplinary access is supported. The digital structures and data modelling open up our data to a wide range of interdisciplinary areas that work with colours or colour terms, and allow querying and access to information also to third parties. In the Digital Humanities context, the data are explored from the perspectives of lexicography, digital infrastructure, visualisation and citizen science. The wealth of available information not only covers dialectal words, but also valuable cultural information about the country and its people [5], and colours are one particular part of it. In this paper we provide first insights into the different angles of exploitation of colour terms, in particular semantic aspects, in the context of the project, the wider European infrastructures, and potentials for related interdisciplinary perspectives.

2. The data - questionnaire on colours and beyond

Questionnaire number 53 (*Farben*) “Colours”, is dedicated to colours and colour terms, and serves as the starting point for the data analysis. It contains around 100 individual questions asking for specific names, synonyms, sayings related to particular colours or traditional beliefs or customs as shown in the examples below.

53D10 grün: der Grünling, Grüner, Grünler (Name von Tieren, Menschen, Pflanzen)

[53D10 green: der Grünling, Grüner, Grünler (name for animals, humans, plants)]

53C1 rot: rot, Wendungen, Vergleiche; VkdL.: Zauberfarbe!, z.B. rote Halsbänder (Schellenbögen) bei Kälbern

[53C1 red: red, phrases, comparisons; popular belief: magic colour!, e.g. red neckband for calves]

Colours covered include *white, yellow, red, blue, green, brown, yellow-brown, grey, black* as well as *pale* and the term *colour* itself. Interestingly, answers do not only contain information on colours, but dip into a variety of other semantic fields in other questionnaires including animal and plant names, food, diseases or the use of colours for specific customs and festivities. Similarly, an initial analysis of *red* showed that our data contain around 90 distinct hues of red such as *brennrot* (burning red), *karmesinrot* (crimson), *kirschrot*

¹ <http://www.oeaw.ac.at/acdh/de/exploreAT>

² Resource Description Framework -- RDF <http://www.w3.org/RDF/> [accessed: Nov 1st 2015]

³ EGI ENGAGE: <https://www.egi.eu/about/egi-engage/>

⁴ DARIAH CC: https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Competence_centre_DARIAH

(cherry red) etc. Mark up for etymological information and semantic concepts is offered using standards such as TEI⁵, thus linking various sources. Our mapping of the lexicographic data onto RDF follows also the intention to be able to represent those interdependencies using the linked open data (LOD)⁶ means. In the LOD framework we can also link to data sets in other scientific fields which are dealing with colours.

With the aid of digital humanities tools it is envisaged to analyse these data in terms of connected semantic concepts and linguistic formation, relevant for lexicographic use. In addition, information on location, time and source of entries are considered, contributing to the application of visual analysis tools, where analysis is currently on the way.

3. European frameworks and contexts

The cross-linguistic and cross-cultural differences in colour terminology have been well and widely studied, see for example [6]. In terms of lexicography, the data described here are also integrated in larger European frameworks and initiatives that the *exploreAT!* project is connected to. These include the Network of electronic Lexicography (COST ENeL)⁷, where colour terms are part of recent projects on etymological dictionaries⁸, and work carried out towards a European Dictionary Portal [7]. As to European infrastructures, the project data is also embedded in the frameworks EGI ENGAGE and DARIAH CC, which enable the link to several other data types, and the discovery of content of digital repositories via semantic search engine. This is another key element in making these colour data accessible to other disciplines.

4. Conclusion and outlook

In this paper we gave an initial insight into the exploitation of colour terms for interdisciplinary research. With the aid of Digital Humanities tools, the data is opened up to analysis from various perspectives, including semantic concepts and lexicography. With the applied data model and the additional development of visual analysis tool and the integration of citizen science, access on a variety of levels to scholars and non-scholars alike is provided. Access to these non-standard data is also supported wider European infrastructures.

5. References

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⁵ www.slideshare.net/JackBowers1

⁶ See <http://linkeddata.org/>

⁷ COST ENeL: COST IS 1305: European network of electronic Lexicography: www.elexicography.eu

⁸ COST ENeL WG4: European Roots <https://sites.google.com/a/campus.ul.pt/european-roots/home>